

The Nexus between Family Enterprises and the Sustainable Growth of Small and Medium-Sized Businesses in Nigeria: A Critical Review

Okafor, Joy Ndidiamaka

Department of Business Administration, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Nigeria

nj.okafor@unizik.edu.ng

ORCID ID: 0009-0006-6934-2369

Anyaegbunam, Chioma Ezinwanne

Department of Business Administration, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University

Igbariam Campus

ezinwannechioma1@gmail.com

Chidi E. Nwokike

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus- Anambra State-Nigeria

Department of Public Administration

nwokikechidi@gmail.com

ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3991-3379

Abstract: The interplay between Family Enterprises (FEs) and Small and Medium-Sized Businesses (SMBs) in Nigeria holds crucial implications for sustainable growth in the evolving global business landscape. This in-depth analysis explored the intricate interplay between these two separate yet interlinked entities. Family-led enterprises and small and medium-sized businesses (SMBs) stand as pivotal catalysts for economic progress, fostering innovation, and fueling the growth of employment opportunities. While family-owned SMBs contribute significantly to Nigeria's economy, their unique dynamics, including succession planning challenges, familial conflicts, and attachment to tradition, can hinder sustained growth. Effective succession planning requires clear guidelines, open communication, and structured processes to navigate conflicts and ensure seamless transitions. Balancing familial ties with professional management necessitates well-defined governance structures to enhance decision-making and transparency. Access to finance remains a key obstacle for SMBs in Nigeria due to limited credit options, high interest rates, and collateral requirements. Moreover, resistance to innovation within family-owned SMBs can hinder adaptation to changing market dynamics. Intensifying competition in Nigeria's SMB sector from domestic and international players underscores the need for family-owned businesses to embrace innovation and recalibrate strategies. To thrive in this competitive landscape, family enterprises must strike a balance between tradition and adaptability while leveraging their strengths and adopting best practices. Recommendations included developing clear succession plans, establishing transparent governance structures, collaborating with financial institutions, promoting innovation, and seeking strategic partnerships to navigate the evolving business environment. Understanding and addressing the nuanced relationship between family enterprises and SMBs are pivotal for fostering sustainable growth and economic development.

Keywords: Family Enterprises, Sustainable Growth, Small and Medium-Sized Businesses, Family-Owned Enterprises

Introduction

In recent decades, the landscape of global business has undergone remarkable transformations, characterized by dynamic shifts in economic paradigms, technological advancements, and changing consumer preferences (Kyove et al., 2021). Amidst this evolving environment, small and medium-sized businesses (SMBs) have emerged as critical drivers of economic development, innovation, and employment generation in various economies worldwide. These enterprises contribute significantly to national GDPs, enhance regional competitiveness, and foster entrepreneurship (Gherghina et al., 2020). Tomášková and Havlíček (2018) asserted that family enterprises have maintained their presence and influence, often serving as the backbone of SMBs. In today's dynamic economic landscape, the intricate interplay between Family Enterprises (FEs) and Small and Medium-Sized Businesses (SMEs) has gained considerable attention due to its far-reaching implications for sustainable growth. Family enterprises, often rooted in a legacy of tradition and shared values, coexist alongside the agile and innovative SMEs, forming the backbone of many economies worldwide (Tomášková and Havlíček, 2018). This research delves into the nuanced connection between these two distinct yet interconnected business entities and their pivotal role in facilitating sustainable growth.

Family enterprises, as the term implies, are businesses owned and managed by one or more families across generations (Olson et al., 2003). Their prevalence spans various sectors and industries, reflecting diverse organizational structures, ranging from small businesses to large conglomerates. On the other hand, SMEs, as defined by their limited scale and resources, play an indispensable role in fostering innovation, creating employment opportunities, and bolstering local economies (Banwo et al., 2017; Ogonu and Okejim, 2018). Their capacity to adapt swiftly to changing market conditions positions them as key players in the business ecosystem. Sustainable growth, a central tenet of modern business philosophy, extends beyond mere financial gains. It encompasses economic viability, environmental responsibility, and social equity, aligning with the principles of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. Sustainable growth prioritizes the long-term well-being of businesses, communities, and ecosystems alike, emphasizing a harmonious coexistence between economic progress and societal welfare. Understanding the nexus between family enterprises and the sustainable growth of SMEs is of paramount importance. This relationship not only influences the trajectory of individual businesses but also has broader implications for regional and national economies (Somboonvechakarn et al., 2022). The distinct characteristics of family enterprises, such as their values-driven decision-making, continuity-focused strategies, and unique governance structures, can significantly impact the growth trajectory of SMEs they interact with (Andersson et al., 2018). Conversely, SMEs bring agility, innovation, and fresh perspectives to family enterprises, enhancing their adaptability and resilience in an ever-evolving business landscape.

As the global business ecosystem continues to evolve, exploring the synergies and potential challenges at the intersection of family enterprises and SMEs becomes imperative. This research aims to unravel the intricate dynamics that shape this relationship and shed light on how it influences the sustainable growth of both entities. This research delves into the intriguing intersection between family enterprises and the sustainable growth of small and medium-sized businesses, unearthing the complexities, challenges, and opportunities that arise from this nexus.

Contextualizing Family Enterprises and Small and Medium-Sized Businesses

Family enterprises, often marked by a concentrated ownership, hands-on management, and a closely-knit leadership circle comprising members of the same family, have played a

pivotal role in shaping economies across generations (Al-Dubai et al., 2014). These entities blend familial values, long-term vision, and personalized involvement to cultivate distinct organizational cultures. Their agility and adaptability stem from the alignment of family interests with business pursuits, enabling swift decision-making and a strong commitment to the enterprise's success. By fostering an environment of trust and shared heritage, family enterprises exhibit resilience in navigating economic uncertainties while simultaneously contributing to employment, innovation, and economic growth. Recognizing their historical significance and intricate dynamics, the study of family enterprises offers insights into the intricate interplay between business, culture, and heritage within economies. Such businesses span various sectors and industries, ranging from retail to manufacturing, from services to technology. With a shared history and a common vision, family enterprises often embody a strong sense of identity, tradition, and stewardship (Harms, 2014).

Ghadoliya's (2020) perspective on family businesses underscores the notion that such enterprises are characterized by the involvement of multiple family members holding financial authority within the company. In essence, a family business encompasses a scenario wherein the ownership and management responsibilities are undertaken by two or more individuals belonging to the same family. This definition highlights the intertwined dynamics of kinship and business, where familial ties intersect with operational decisions and strategic direction. Such businesses are not solely bound by conventional corporate hierarchies but also encompass the unique complexities and interplay of family relationships within the realm of commerce. Chua et al., (1999) characterize family businesses (FBs) as entities with a central vision driven by a dominant coalition composed of family members or a small network of families. This vision is designed to endure across successive generations, signifying a core element of FB essence. Habbershon et al., (2003) introduced the concept of "familiness" as an essential trait of Family Businesses. Their assertion suggests that family businesses harbor a distinctive assemblage of assets and competencies arising from the complex interplay amid the familial collective, the corporate establishment, and individual kin. This "familiness" sets FBs apart from other businesses.

Family enterprises constitute a substantial and lasting dimension of the worldwide economy, playing a pivotal role in fostering employment opportunities, driving innovation, and nurturing the growth of local communities. Defining the essence of a family business is a complex task, as it involves the intersection of family dynamics and business operations. The above definitions captured following notable features of family of business:

- i. **Collective Family Involvement:** At the heart of a family business lies a group of individuals who share familial ties, collectively taking charge of a single business entity. These persons might have affiliations with one or multiple households, yet they synergize their efforts to propel the enterprise ahead. The intertwining of personal bonds with business endeavors creates a unique blend of passion, commitment, and shared purpose that often distinguishes family businesses from their corporate counterparts.
- ii. **Influence of Interpersonal Relationships:** Positional hierarchy within a family business is not solely dictated by formal organizational structures. Instead, it is significantly shaped by the interpersonal relationships that family members share. These relationships can influence decision-making, the delegation of responsibilities, and the overall harmony of the business environment. The familial bonds that

- underpin these relationships can foster both collaboration and challenges, which, in turn, affect the business's dynamics.
- iii. **Dual Control: Ownership and Management:** The family's control over the business manifests in two key ways: through ownership and through management. Family members may possess ownership stakes in the company, giving them a tangible financial stake in its success. Additionally, family members can hold vital managerial positions, leveraging their expertise and commitment to steer the enterprise towards prosperity. This dual control often results in a holistic approach to business management, blending both financial interests and familial values.
 - iv. **Influence on Strategic Direction:** Family businesses often uphold a distinct ethos, with values and aspirations intrinsically linked to the family's identity. As such, the family's influence extends beyond the operational aspects of the business to encompass strategic decisions. The policies and directions taken by the business are frequently shaped by the family's collective vision, balancing the interests of both kinship and commerce.
 - v. **Generational Succession:** A hallmark feature of family businesses is the continuity they seek across generations. As the current generation of family members manages the enterprise, plans for succession to the next generation are crucial. This succession planning involves preparing heirs to assume leadership roles, ensuring a seamless transition of ownership and management.

On the other hand, Small and Medium-Sized Businesses though varying in scale, often exhibit traits of nimbleness, adaptability, and innovation. Their contributions to job creation and economic growth cannot be overstated, especially in emerging economies where they constitute a substantial portion of the business ecosystem. The SME sector is crucial in the modern economy due to its innovation and attractiveness. SMEs vary in employee count across industries. SMEs contribute to job creation, consumer satisfaction, and market competition, assisting larger enterprises. They also focus on innovation, aiding GDP growth, national export, and social-political stability. SME finance involves funding for these enterprises, which includes bank loans, equity issuance, venture capital, and government grants. While SMEs need financing for various lifecycle stages, challenges like information asymmetry and limited financial skills persist. Entrepreneurship drives economic growth, but barriers such as regulations, access to finance, and knowledge utilization need to be addressed, ensuring inclusivity. Productivity, defined as output per input, drives long-term economic growth. Factors affecting SME productivity include competition, trade openness, skills, innovation, and access to resources. Digitalization offers SMEs global exposure, innovation opportunities, and growth potential, but adoption remains uneven (Al-Herwi, 2019).

In Nigeria, as well as in global economies, delineating a business's classification hinges on pivotal determinants. These determinants primarily revolve around the expanse of its operations. These variables typically encompass the extent of capital invested in assets, the aggregate annual turnover the business generates, and the tally of its workforce (Adamu and Ibrahim, 2011). Collectively, these yardsticks function as metrics to assess the dimensions, reach, and economic reverberations of enterprises. Through the evaluation of these constituents, regulatory bodies can adeptly slot businesses into diverse categories. This stratification subsequently aids in crafting well-suited regulations, structures for taxation, and policies that cater to the distinctive requisites of businesses of varying magnitudes. This modus operandi is imperative to cultivate an environment conducive to business expansion and economic

advancement, concurrently ensuring equitable handling of enterprises spanning a spectrum of sizes. Adamu and Ibrahim (2011) see a medium-scale enterprise as a company with operational assets below N200 million and a workforce of fewer than 300 individuals. On the other hand, a small-scale enterprise is characterized by total assets not exceeding N50 million and having fewer than 100 employees. Interestingly, annual turnover is not a determining factor in the definition of these Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). The National Economic Reconstruction Fund (NERFUND) introduces a further category, designating a Small-Scale Enterprise (SSE) as one with total assets lower than N10 million, without specifying annual turnover or employee count as defining criteria.

Carter and Jones-Evans, as cited in the work of Berisha and Pula (2015), provided a distinct perspective on defining Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) that takes into account the relative size of firms within their specific contexts. This approach acknowledges that the classification of a business as small, medium, or large is not solely determined by its absolute numerical measures but also by the relative scale within its market and sector. In essence, an enterprise operating in a substantial market within a specific industry might still be classified as small due to its relative size in comparison to other larger players in that same market. Conversely, a business functioning in a smaller market within a particular industry could be labeled as medium or even large when considered in the context of its market and industry. This approach underscores the importance of considering the nuanced dynamics of markets and industries when categorizing SMEs, rather than relying solely on fixed numerical criteria.

The Interplay: Family Enterprises and of Small and Medium-Sized Businesses

In Nigeria, the business landscape is notably marked by a considerable prevalence of family-owned enterprises, frequently aligning with the classification of small and medium-sized businesses (SMBs). These familial ventures hold a pivotal role in driving the country's economic engine, wielding substantial influence through their substantial contributions to both employment generation and revenue generation. Despite their valuable contributions, these family-owned SMBs encounter a distinctive set of operational dynamics. The presence of family members within the business hierarchy, coupled with intricate succession planning hurdles and a prevailing emphasis on upholding ancestral heritage, collectively exert an intricate influence that can impede the realization of sustained growth objectives.

Effective succession planning within family-owned SMBs in Nigeria is a critical yet challenging endeavour. The transition of leadership from one generation to another is often hindered by several factors. Familial conflicts can arise due to differing opinions and aspirations among family members, potentially leading to disputes that impede a smooth transition (West, 2019). According to Awosanya (2019), the absence of clear guidelines and structured processes for succession can contribute to confusion and uncertainty, creating an environment where conflicts thrive. Moreover, the emotional attachment of founders and current leaders to the business can foster a reluctance to cede control, which further complicates the succession process. Addressing these challenges requires a delicate balance between family dynamics, open communication, and the establishment of well-defined succession plans to ensure the continuity and sustainable growth of these family enterprises.

Balancing the inherent dynamics of a family-owned business with the demands for professional management presents a delicate challenge. Family enterprises often find themselves torn between the familial ties that shape their identity and the necessity of adopting rigorous business practices to ensure growth and sustainability. One key obstacle is the deficiency in

effective governance structures. Many family businesses in Nigeria lack well-defined frameworks for decision-making, strategic planning, and accountability (West, 2019). This inadequacy has the potential to result in ambiguous responsibilities, contradictory objectives, and an absence of openness. As a result, crucial decisions might be delayed or made without due consideration, potentially hindering the business's ability to respond promptly and adeptly to market changes. Furthermore, the absence of formalization in areas like succession planning, management roles, and conflict resolution can exacerbate these challenges. When roles and responsibilities are not clearly outlined, family dynamics can overshadow objective decision-making, leading to friction and impeding the development of a cohesive growth strategy.

Access to finance remains a critical challenge for small and medium-sized businesses (SMBs) in Nigeria, hindering their growth and expansion (Gumel and Bardai, 2021). This issue arises from a combination of factors that create barriers to obtaining the necessary funding for operational continuity and development. Traditional financial institutions, such as banks, may be hesitant to lend to smaller businesses due to perceived higher risks and limited credit history. This scarcity of available credit sources restricts SMBs' ability to secure the funds required to invest in growth initiatives. Even when credit is available, the prevailing high interest rates in Nigeria can place a substantial financial burden on SMBs. This financial strain can curtail the growth prospects of SMBs, making it difficult to compete effectively in the market. Financial institutions in Nigeria often require significant collateral as a condition for granting loans. For many SMBs, especially those operating in sectors with intangible assets or limited valuable collateral, meeting these requirements can be challenging. The difficulty in accessing finance has direct implications for the growth trajectory and innovation potential of SMBs. These businesses require capital injections to invest in research and development, marketing, technology adoption, and human resources. Without adequate financing, SMBs are forced to operate within the confines of limited resources, impeding their capacity to innovate, diversify, and seize new market opportunities.

In the context of family enterprises in Nigeria, a noteworthy challenge arises from their inclination to uphold traditional practices, which can impede their capacity to effectively embrace innovation and adapt to evolving market dynamics and technological advancements. According to Yua (2019), the attachment to established methods and values, often rooted in the desire to maintain a legacy, can create resistance to change and hinder the enterprise's agility in responding to external shifts. This resistance to innovation can limit the family business's ability to capture emerging opportunities, respond to competitive pressures, and engage with evolving consumer preferences. As markets transform and technology reshapes industries, family-owned SMBs may find themselves falling behind more adaptable competitors. The reluctance to depart from conventional approaches might restrict the integration of new ideas, processes, and technologies that could optimize operations, enhance products or services, and open doors to previously untapped markets.

In recent years, the competitive landscape within Nigeria's small and medium-sized business (SMB) sector has undergone a substantial transformation, marked by a notable escalation in competitive pressures. This intensification of competition can be attributed to a confluence of factors, including the growing presence of domestic players, the ingress of international entrants, and the enticing prospects presented by Nigeria's rapidly expanding market economy (African Food Changemakers, 2016). This changing dynamic within the SMB sector has created an environment characterized by heightened rivalry and strategic maneuvering. Traditionally, family-owned businesses have been pivotal players in Nigeria's

economic fabric, often occupying prominent positions across various industries. However, in the face of this mounting competition, these enterprises find themselves at a crucial crossroads, compelled to recalibrate their approaches and navigate the evolving terrain with acumen and innovation (International Trade Administration, 2023). The entrance of international players into Nigeria's business landscape has introduced an additional layer of complexity. These global entrants are drawn by the country's abundant opportunities, burgeoning consumer base, and promising economic indicators. Their participation in the market has introduced a new set of benchmarks and best practices, raising the standards of competition. As such, family-owned businesses, previously accustomed to a certain market equilibrium, are now presented with the urgent need to elevate their operational efficacy and strategic differentiation.

Conclusion

The intricate interplay between Family Enterprises (FEs) and Small and Medium-Sized Businesses (SMBs) in Nigeria, as explored in this critical review, reveals a complex relationship with far-reaching implications for sustainable growth. Against the backdrop of a dynamic and evolving global business landscape, family enterprises and SMBs emerge as vital contributors to economic development, innovation, and employment generation. Family enterprises, rooted in tradition and shared values, coexist alongside agile and innovative SMBs, collectively forming the backbone of economies worldwide. The examination of this nexus highlights the multifaceted challenges and opportunities inherent in their interaction. Family-owned SMBs play a significant role in Nigeria's economic fabric, contributing to employment and revenue generation. However, their unique dynamics, including succession planning hurdles, familial conflicts, and attachment to tradition, can hinder sustained growth. Effective succession planning emerges as a critical factor for ensuring the continuity of family enterprises, necessitating clear guidelines, open communication, and structured processes to address conflicts and ensure smooth transitions. The balance between familial ties and professional management presents a delicate challenge for family enterprises. The absence of well-defined governance structures can lead to unclear roles, conflicting interests, and a lack of transparency, hindering effective decision-making and strategic planning. Access to finance remains a key challenge for SMBs, particularly in Nigeria, where limited credit options, high interest rates, and collateral requirements impede growth and innovation. The reluctance to embrace innovation within small and medium-sized businesses (SMBs) that are family-owned could impede their capacity to adjust to shifting market dynamics and the rapid progress of technology. As competition intensifies in Nigeria's SMB sector due to the influx of domestic and international players, family-owned businesses must recalibrate their strategies and embrace innovation to remain competitive. The evolving business landscape underscores the need for family enterprises to balance tradition with adaptability, leveraging their unique strengths while adopting best practices to thrive in a competitive environment.

Recommendations

- i. Develop clear succession plans, involving external advisors if needed, to minimize conflicts and ensure smooth leadership transitions.
- ii. Establish transparent governance structures, hold regular board meetings, and clarify roles to enhance decision-making and reduce conflicts.
- iii. Collaborate with financial institutions for tailored financing solutions, including lower-interest loans and support for businesses with limited collateral.

- iv. Encourage innovation through workshops, training, and resource allocation, fostering adaptability and forward-thinking.
- v. Promote partnerships with other businesses for shared resources and market strength, especially in response to growing competition.

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